

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Radiation Hardened ASIC Telecommand Interface for Space Applications (TCMDatKU)</i>
Project TA identifier	TA08-236
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
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Facility	RADEF - University of Jyväskylä
Amount of access granted	16h

Objectives of the experiments

The Low-Voltage High-Power Command Circuit (LV-HPC) is a critical component in satellite power management systems, enabling low-voltage control signals from the onboard computer to switch and drive high-power loads such as radio frequency amplifiers, electric propulsion units, and thermal control subsystems. It is essential because command and telemetry units typically operate at low voltage and low current levels, whereas many spacecraft subsystems require high current that cannot be directly supplied by these control circuits. To ensure reliable operation in the harsh space environment, these circuits are designed with key features such as high reliability, radiation hardness, and robust fault protection mechanisms, including current limiting and thermal shutdown. Additionally, they are optimized for low power loss and minimal thermal dissipation, which are critical constraints in satellite due to limited power availability and thermal control capacity. We designed a LV-HPC using a proposed Redundancy

Hardening by Design (RHBD) technique. This approach incorporates Enclosed Layout Transistors (ELTs) and a redundancy topology, in which each standard transistor is replaced by four ELTs arranged in a series-parallel configuration, as presented in [1].

Power transistors (PTs) are critical components across a variety of applications. They are commonly used to handle high current loads, function as smart power switches, and provide protection in satellite power distribution systems. As part of ongoing projects involving the use of PTs by our research team, two commercial devices were selected for evaluation under defined test conditions.

Therefore, the primary objectives of this study were to conduct radiation testing and characterization under high-energy particle exposure to evaluate the susceptibility, functional robustness, and reliability of the following components and subsystems:

- Overall performance of the LV-HPC circuit under radiation stress conditions.
- Independent functional behaviour and radiation response of individual subcircuits within the LV-HPC architecture.
- Effectiveness of the proposed RHBD techniques in mitigating radiation-induced degradation and functional anomalies.
- Radiation tolerance and failure thresholds of two commercially available power transistors under high-energy particle exposure.

On the other hand, in collaboration with the Center for Information Technology Renato Archer and the Mauá Institute of Technology, a high-speed fault detection measurement circuit based on FPGA was developed to identify Single Event Effects (SEEs). The radiation tests also aimed to evaluate the functionality of this measurement system.

Experiment test report

The LV-HPC was fabricated using 0.6 μm Silicon-On-Insulator (SOI) technology, which intrinsically mitigates latch-up effects due to substrate isolation. The block diagram and corresponding timing diagram of the LV-HPC circuit are shown in Fig. 1, comprising two independent control channels. The operating voltages include 5 V for general and telemetry supply rails (VDD5 and VDD5TM), and 14 V for the power stage (VPOW). The output driver stage boosts the logic-level control signal from 5 V to a 14 V gate drive.

The load current is limited via a current-limiting circuit that scales a 20 μA reference current to a maximum output of 400 mA. Overcurrent detection is also implemented, with a threshold set at approximately 180 mA.

The key subcircuits and their respective functions include the following:

- **Driver Stage (Outputdriver_x)** – Generates the necessary gate voltage to switch the PMOS power transistor.
- **PMOS Power Transistor** – Functions as an analog high-side power switch for load control.

- **Current Limiter (ICUT)** – Restricts the output current to prevent overload and short-circuit conditions by scaling a reference current.
- **Voltage and Current Telemetry Blocks (TC and TV)** – Perform real-time monitoring of the output voltage and current for system diagnostics.
- **Overcurrent Detector (OVC)** – Monitors the output current and signals a fault condition when a predefined threshold is exceeded.
- **Output State Monitor (St_out)** – Indicates the operational status of the telecommand output channels.

Figure 1. Block diagram and corresponding timing diagram of the LV-HPC circuit

The selected power transistors for radiation testing are N-channel MOSFETs (ON Semiconductor) — FDD86326 and FDD86252 — which offer the following specifications:

- FDD86326: 80 V drain-source voltage (V_{DS}), continuous drain currents up to 37 A (T_c), and an on-resistance (R_{on}) as low as 23 m Ω .
- FDD86252: 150 V drain-source voltage (V_{DS}), continuous drain currents up to 27 A (T_c), and an on-resistance (R_{on}) approximately 52 m Ω .

2) Test Bench Setup

The proposed detection circuit was implemented on the Terasic DE10-Lite FPGA development board, selected for its high sampling frequency and processing capabilities. The circuit adopts a modular architecture consisting of four main components. The first is a General State Machine Module, which manages the operational states of the system. The second is the Pulse Counter and Timestamps Module,

essential for the digital detection of SEEs; it monitors 3.3V LTTTL pulses, records precise timestamps for each event, generates trigger signals for external oscilloscopes to enable high-resolution waveform capture, and includes filters to suppress metastability and noise, ensuring reliable SEE identification. The third component is an Artificial Signal Generator Module, used to simulate SEEs and validate the circuit's functionality by generating deterministic digital pulses on specific channels. The final component is the Data Processing and Communication Module, which employs a Nios II soft-core processor to manage memory allocation, process captured data, and handle RS232-UART communication. This module also receives user commands for system control and remote data retrieval, which is particularly important during radiation testing. A more detailed description of the circuit is provided in [2].

Fig. 2 shows the LV-HPC board connected to the detection and measurement circuit used during the radiation testing of the LV-HPC and its subcircuits.

Figure 2. LV-HPC and detection measurement circuit

Table I presents a list of the systems and devices that were monitored during the radiation test. Each component was designated as DUTx (Device Under Test). The experiments were conducted on three LV-HPC boards using a typical functional setup, with specific signals being monitored. Additionally, certain internal blocks were observed through an alternative connection on the LV-HPC board. The commercial PTs were tested separately.

Table I – List of Systems and Devices Monitored During the Radiation Test

Name	Description
DUT1	LV-HPC Board 1
DUT2	LV-HPC Board 2
DUT3	LV-HPC Board 3
DUT4	LV-HPC - Power Transistors
DUT5	LV-HPC - Current Mirror
DUT6	FDD86326 – NMOS Power Transistor
DUT7	FDD86326 – NMOS Power Transistor
DUT8	FDD86252 – NMOS Power Transistor

DUT1-DUT3: LV-HPC

To minimize transient disturbances resulting from switching activity, the three LV-HPC boards were configured in a steady state operating mode, thereby allowing the observation of voltage spikes exclusively induced by SEEs. Therefore, the gate terminal of the power transistors and the power stage were supplied by a 3.3 V voltage source. The input channel CC1 was connected to 3.3 V, while CC2 was connected to ground. The general supply of the LV-HPC was set to 5 V, and the system remained enabled by connecting the EN pin to 3.3 V. Table II summarizes the operating states, bias conditions, and monitored pin connections used in the test setup.

Table II – Operating States, Bias Conditions, and Monitored Pins Used in the SEE Test Setup

Name Pin	Connection	S. State	Bias
S1	S1 and S2 shorted	3V3	3V3
S2	S1 and S2 shorted	3V3	3V3
D1	10 M Ω to GND	0V	GND
D2	10 M Ω to GND	0V	GND
ICUT	10 M Ω to GND	3V3	--
Outdriver_1	10 M Ω to VDD	0V	GND
Outdriver_2	10 M Ω to VDD	3V3	--
OVC	10 M Ω to V5		3V3
ST_OUT	10 M Ω to V5		3V3
TC	10 M Ω to GND	Analog	--
TV	01 M Ω to GND	Analog	--

DUT4: LV-HPC - Power Transistors

The LV-HPC includes two power transistors (PTs), which were implemented using the proposed RHBD technique, i.e., a series/parallel configuration composed of four transistors. The two PTs were connected in parallel and coupled to a 10 M Ω resistive load. The LV-HPC power supply (VPOW) was connected to ground to minimize potential disturbances to nearby devices. The gate and source terminals of the PTs were biased at 3.3 V, resulting in $V_{GS}=0$ V. The voltage across the load was monitored during the tests.

DUT5: LV-HPC - Current Mirror

The current mirror was tested using the same experimental setup as for the PT (DUT4), by monitoring the voltage across a 10 M Ω resistor connected in series with the mirror's output at the ICUT terminal of the LV-HPC.

DUT6- DUT8: Commercial PT

The power transistors were individually mounted with the gate and source terminals shorted and biased at 5 V. A 10 M Ω load was connected to the drain terminal. During the radiation testing, the drain voltage of each transistor was continuously monitored

3) Results and discussion

The test components were irradiated using a 16.3 MeV/u ion cocktail in air mode, with a flux of 5×10^3 ions/s/cm² and a total fluence of 9×10^5 ions/cm² over seven measurement cycles. During each cycle, one ion was chosen from the available ions: ¹⁷O, ²⁰Ne, ⁴⁰Ar, ⁵⁷Fe, ⁸³Kr, ¹⁰⁷Ag, and ¹²⁶Xe. DUT1 and DUT2 were subjected to three additional irradiation cycles at an increased flux of 1×10^4 ions/s/cm² for ¹²⁶Xe, reaching a cumulative fluence of 3.6×10^6 ions/cm². Similarly, DUT3 underwent three additional cycles at a flux of 5×10^3 ions/s/cm², resulting in a total fluence of 1.8×10^6 ions/cm². In the final test cycles, a Linear Energy Transfer (LET) of 69 MeV·cm²/mg was applied using degraders of 50 μm and 100 μm thickness to reduce the ion energy and achieve the desired LET at the device surface. **Fig. 3** presents the time-dependent particle flux profiles corresponding to multiple SEE test runs carried out on the device under test.

Fig. 4 highlights the LV-HPC and the detection circuit positioned in front of the ion accelerator, along with the test and control room where the SEE tests were conducted.

Figure 3. Applied particle flux profile over time during SEE testing of the DUT.

Figure 4. Setup for SEE testing: TCMD and detection circuits positioned in front of the ion accelerator, with test and control room.

No significant SEEs were observed during the tests conducted on the LV-HPC circuit (DUT1, DUT2, and DUT3). However, during irradiation cycles with high-energy ions and after the accumulation of a certain total ionizing dose, SEEs were observed in the state-monitor circuit and in the current-mirror. The state-monitor circuit comprises a resistive voltage divider followed by an open-drain NMOS transistor (ST_out) with a 10 MΩ pull-up resistor. Although these circuits exhibited SEE-induced perturbations, their functional operation was not compromised. No SEEs were detected in the remaining devices.

Both types of commercial power transistors (FDD86326 and FDD86252) were subjected to heavy-ion irradiation. Fig. 5 presents the $I_{DS} - V_{GS}$ characteristics. Both transistors were biased at $V_{DS}=1$. Each C_x (where $x=1, \dots, 10$) corresponds to the result obtained after each irradiation cycle. In successive cycles, the ion mass was increased, along with the incident beam flux. No destructive SEE were observed during testing. However, both devices exhibited significant degradation as a function of the accumulated total ionizing dose (TID). The threshold voltage decreased, while the leakage current increased, causing the devices to turn on even at negative gate voltages for a certain TID level.

a) b)
Figure 5. $I_{DS} - V_{GS}$ characteristics of both transistors: (a) FDD86326 and (b) FDD86252

• **Conclusion**

The LV-HPC circuit functioned correctly across all conducted tests. Additionally, the isolated subcircuit demonstrated no significant sensitivity to SEE, even under exposure to heavy ions. These results indicate that the overall system design exhibits robust performance in radiation environments. Furthermore, the proposed RHBD technique, which employs ELT transistors and a redundant architecture, proves to be a promising approach for enhancing the radiation tolerance of ICs.

The proposed measurement circuit, designed for the detection of SEEs in digital signals, proved to be effective by operating correctly and successfully capturing SEEs during the conducted tests. These initial results validate its functionality and provide valuable data for future analysis.

Nevertheless, further testing is necessary to validate the IC design, assess the effectiveness of the proposed RHBD technique, and verify the performance of the developed SEE detection circuit.

• **References**

[1] R. H. G. Chacón et al., "A Radiation Hardened Smart Power Switch Based on SOI Technology," 2023 IEEE 14th Latin America Symposium on Circuits and Systems (LASCAS), Quito, Ecuador, 2023, pp. 1-4, [doi: 10.1109/LASCAS56464.2023.10108134](https://doi.org/10.1109/LASCAS56464.2023.10108134).

[2] L. H. A. Santos, R. M. França, S. Finco, D. D. V. Gueter, and V. C. Parro, "Development of an FPGA-Based Measurement Circuit for Detecting High-Speed Single Event Effects in Radiation-Hardened ASICs," in Proc. VII Workshop on the Effects of Ionizing Radiation in Electronic Components and Circuits for Aerospace Use (WERICE Aeroespacial 2024), São José dos Campos, Brazil, Nov. 4–6, 2024. [Online]. Available: https://eventos.congresso.me/werice_aeroespacial_2024/edicoes/WERICE_AEROESPACIAL_2024

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	X
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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